

Appendix 4. Participant consent form examples

Makerere University College of Health Sciences; Supporting Informed Healthcare Choices in Low-Income Countries Project.

RESEARCH PARTICIPANT'S ASSENT FORM-ENGLISH

Project title: Supporting Informed Healthcare Choices in Low-Income Countries (SIHCLIC). Version 1.0 dated: 14 August 2012.

Sponsor: The Research Council of Norway

Study Principal Investigator: Prof. Nelson K Sewankambo

Co-investigators: Ms. Allen Nsangi
Dr. Daniel Semakula

Addresses: Makerere University, College of Health Sciences
New Mulago Hospital Complex, Clinical Research Building, 2nd Floor
P.O Box 7072, Kampala, Uganda
Phone:0312109456

Date/Revision: Version 1.1 (1st August 2014)

Introduction.

We are doing a research study about how people can be helped to understand and assess information that concerns their health. A research study is a way to learn more about people, how they live their lives and how they make decisions about their lives and what happens to them when they make decisions.

We are asking you to participate in this study because we think that your contribution will help us develop materials that can help children like you understand and assess information about their health.

First of all, there are some things about this study you should know.

Participation in this study is purely voluntary and you may feel free not to join or to stop participating if you feel uncomfortable with the study activities at any time after joining. Your parents/guardians know about this study. If you do not want to be in this research study, you will not be penalised.

If you decide that you want to be part of this study, we may follow you up for about 2-3 years. During this time we may give you or your teacher some of the materials we shall develop and then ask you some questions at different time points to find out if the materials helped you understand and assess health information or not.

Benefits to you.

There will be no direct benefits to you but we think that by participating in this study you will receive free health information.

SIHCLIC- English Assent Form. Version 1.1-01-August-2014

MAKERERE UNIVERSITY
SCHOOL OF MEDICINE
APPROVED
VALID UNTIL
* 22 AUG 2015 *

RESEARCH & ETHICS COMMITTEE
P.O. BOX 7072, KAMPALA, UGANDA

Makerere University College of Health Sciences; Supporting Informed Healthcare Choices in Low-Income Countries Project.

Possible risks to you.

We do not anticipate the study to cause you any harm, risks or dangers. We do not think that your school performance will be affected by participating in this research.

Confidentiality.

If you choose to participate all the information you give us will be kept as a secret and it will not bear your name or your parent/guardian's name.

When we are finished with this study we will write a report about what was learned. This report will not include your name or that you were in the study.

If you have understood everything about the study and all your questions have been answered, and you decide you want to be in this study, please sign your name below. But if you don't want to be in the study it is still ok, don't sign this paper. Signing below means that you have understood, and you are willing to join the study.

Study Participant

Your signature: _____ Date _____

Your name: _____ Date _____

Staff obtaining assent

Signature of person obtaining assent: _____ Date _____

Printed name of person obtaining assent: _____ Date _____

Witness

Signature of Witness: _____ Date _____

Printed name of Witness: _____ Date _____

Makerere University College of Health Sciences; Supporting Informed Healthcare Choices in Low-Income Countries Project.

RESEARCH PARTICIPANT'S ASSENT FORM-ENGLISH

Project title: Supporting Informed Healthcare Choices in Low-Income Countries (SIHCLIC). Version 1.0 dated: 14 August 2012.

Sponsor: The Research Council of Norway

Study Principal Investigator: Prof. Nelson K Sewankambo

Co-investigators: Ms. Allen Nsangi
Dr. Daniel Semakula

Addresses: Makerere University, College of Health Sciences
New Mulago Hospital Complex, Clinical Research Building, 2nd Floor
P.O Box 7072, Kampala, Uganda
Phone:0312109456

Date/Revision: Version 1.1 (1st August 2014)

Introduction.

We are doing a research study about how people can be helped to understand and assess information that concerns their health. A research study is a way to learn more about people, how they live their lives and how they make decisions about their lives and what happens to them when they make decisions.

We are asking you to participate in this study because we think that your contribution will help us develop materials that can help children like you understand and assess information about their health.

First of all, there are some things about this study you should know.

Participation in this study is purely voluntary and you may feel free not to join or to stop participating if you feel uncomfortable with the study activities at any time after joining. Your parents/guardians know about this study. If you do not want to be in this research study, you will not be penalised.

If you decide that you want to be part of this study, we may follow you up for about 2-3 years. During this time we may give you or your teacher some of the materials we shall develop and then ask you some questions at different time points to find out if the materials helped you understand and assess health information or not.

Benefits to you.

There will be no direct benefits to you but we think that by participating in this study you will receive free health information.

Makerere University College of Health Sciences; Supporting Informed. Healthcare Choices in Low-Income Countries Project.

Possible risks to you.

We do not anticipate the study to cause you any harm, risks or dangers. We do not think that your school performance will be affected by participating in this research.

Confidentiality.

If you choose to participate all the information you give us will be kept as a secret and it will not bear your name or your parent/guardian's name.

When we are finished with this study we will write a report about what was learned. This report will not include your name or that you were in the study.

If you have understood everything about the study and all your questions have been answered, and you decide you want to be in this study, please sign your name below. But if you don't want to be in the study it is still ok, don't sign this paper. Signing below means that you have understood, and you are willing to join the study.

Study Participant

Your signature: _____

Date _____

Your name: _____

Date _____

Staff obtaining assent

Signature of person obtaining assent: _____

Date _____

Printed name of person obtaining assent: _____

Date _____

Witness

Signature of Witness: _____

Date _____

Printed name of Witness: _____

Date _____

TEACHER'S FEEDBACK CONSENT FORM
on behalf of whole class

Research project: Informed Healthcare Choices [your study name]
Research funder: [Your funding institution]
Principal investigator: [Your principal investigator]
Addresses: [Your address]
Email: [Your contact email]

Introduction

We are writing a book that will help children to assess claims and make informed choices about treatments.

We would like your class to help us make this book better.

They only need to help us if they want to.

What will happen if they help us?

All of the children in your science class have read the book. The book is called *The Health Choices Book*. There are 10 chapters in the book.

If you decide it is OK for them to help us, a researcher will come to your class and ask the students some questions about the book. We will ask them questions about the book to find out more about their experiences of it. There are no right or wrong answers to these questions. The session will take about 40 minutes. If it is OK with you and none of the children object, we will record the session. We will use the recording to listen to after the session and make sure that we have understood what they have told us. We will erase the recording after we have done that.

What are the benefits and harms of helping us?

The students will be taking part in real research and they will be helping us make our book better; we think they will learn some interesting and useful things too. Neither you nor they will get any rewards.

The information they give us will not include any of their names. When we have finished writing the book, we will write a report about what we learned. In this report, we will not include your name or any of the children's names.

Do you have any questions about this project?

If you want to know more before you decide whether you want to help us, you can ask one of the researchers.

If you have understood everything in this letter, if all your questions have been answered, and if you decide you want to help us, by allowing us to get feedback from your class, please sign your name below.

[your footer]

Signing below means that you have understood and you are agreeing to allow us to collect feedback from your class by asking them some questions about the *Claims, comparisons and choices* book and their experiences of using it.

TEACHER CONSENT

If you have any questions about this study, please contact the principal investigator using the email address at the top of this form. If you agree that your class can take part, as described above, please sign your name below.

Class:

Teacher's name:

Signature: _____ Date: _____

Makerere University College of Health Sciences; Supporting Informed Healthcare Choices in Low-Income Countries Project.

RESEARCH PARTICIPANT INFORMED CONSENT FORM-ENGLISH

Project title: Supporting Informed Healthcare Choices in Low-Income Countries (SIHCLIC). Version 1.0 dated: 14 August 2012.

Sponsor: The Research Council of Norway

Study Principal Investigator: Prof. Nelson K. Sewankambo

Co-investigators: Ms. Allen Nsangi
Dr. Daniel Semakula

Addresses: Makerere University, College of Health Sciences
New Mulago Hospital Complex, Clinical Research Building, 2nd Floor
P.O Box 7072, Kampala, Uganda
Phone: 0312109456

Date/Revision: Version 1.1 (1st August 2014)

1. INTRODUCTION.

The Supporting Informed Healthcare Choices in Low-Income Countries (SIHCLIC) Project is a research collaboration that seeks to improve health literacy by developing and testing of resources that can be used by the public to appraise health information.

In Uganda, the study is being conducted by researchers from Makerere University College of Health Sciences and will involve continuous interaction with journalists, teachers and children.

The information in this document is meant to help you decide whether or not to take part in this study but first there a few things to note.

- You are being asked to participate in this research because you are a journalist/media practitioner or teacher or a potential recipient of information from journalists/media practitioners or teachers; and an adult of legal consenting age.
- We anticipate that once you agree to participate you will be in the study for a period of 5 years or less.
- You will be offered a copy of this form for your future reference.
- Please feel free to ask if you have any questions or concerns at any time before the start or during the conduct of the research.

2. WHY IS THIS RESEARCH BEING CONDUCTED?

The aim of this collaborative research project is to improve population health outcomes by improving health literacy in low-income countries. We will do this by developing and evaluating two strategies for improving health literacy: development and evaluation of mass media resources for the general public and the development and evaluation of teaching resources for school children.

SIHCLIC- English Informed Consent Form for journalists, teachers and their audiences Version 1.1 Aug 2014

Makerere University College of Health Sciences; Supporting Informed Healthcare Choices in Low-Income Countries Project.

3. HOW WILL THE STUDY BE CONDUCTED?

This project will be implemented using two strategies for improving health literacy:

- i) The development of mass media resources to improve the ability of the general public to understand and appraise information about the effects of health care.
- ii) The development of teaching resources for school children to improve their ability to appraise and use information about the effects of health care services/interventions made available to them.

These strategies will be evaluated in two community trials testing the effectiveness of the developed resources in improving health literacy among the target audiences for teachers and mass media practitioners/journalists.

The Research project will be conducted under 3 different phases, one following the other.

- Phase one will include: **Priority setting and stakeholder involvement.**
- The second phase will focus on **Resource development and user testing.**
- Phase three will concentrate on **Evaluation of the resources** developed.

4. POSSIBLE RISKS TO YOU:

We anticipate that your participation in the study/research presents no risk to you as an individual. However, participation in this study might in some way interfere with your work if you are required to participate in study activities during work hours.

5. POSSIBLE BENEFITS TO YOU.

There will be no direct benefit to you from participating in this study and there is no promise of gaining any material or financial benefit from the project currently or in the future.

Your participation in the study could contribute to gaining new knowledge that will be used to design resources aimed at improving population health outcomes by improving health literacy in low-income countries. You will be equipped with skills to enable you obtain, process and understand health information that you need to make appropriate healthcare decisions.

You will benefit from free health information.

6. COST TO THE PARTICIPANT.

You will incur no cost whatsoever other than time as a result of taking part in the study.

7. COMPENSATION.

You will not gain any form of compensation, monetary or otherwise for participating in the study but appropriate daily expenses in form of lunch and transport will be reimbursed if you attend any study-related meetings or workshops.

8. CONFIDENTIALITY.

The information you give during the conduct of this research will be kept confidential in accordance to the ethical standards agreed upon by the local and international organizations governing the conduct of research involving human participants.

Any information resulting from this study, if published in scientific journals or presented at scientific meetings, will not reveal your identity.

SIHCLIC- English Informed Consent Form for journalists, teachers and their audiences Version 1.1 Aug 2014.

Makerere University College of Health Sciences; Supporting Informed Healthcare Choices in Low-Income Countries Project.

9. RIGHT TO REFUSE/WITHDRAW.

Your participation in this research is purely voluntary and you are free to decline to take part or withdraw at anytime without any repercussions.

10. QUESTIONS ABOUT THE RESEARCH

In case of any further questions, please contact Professor Nelson K. Sewankambo, the Principal Investigator at Makerere University College of Health Sciences, P.O. Box 7072, Kampala Uganda: Tel: 0414 530021 or Ms Allen Nsangi and Dr. Daniel Semakula, co-investigators on 0773333629 or 0716543000.

In case of questions in regards to research ethics, you may contact Prof. James Tumwine, Chairperson, MakCHS School of Medicine Research and Ethics Committee. Tel: 0414 531875.

11. DECLARATION OF CONSENT

The information about this study has been availed and explained to me and all my questions have been answered. I have read this form and I feel that I have had enough information and time to consider my decision to join the study. I fully understand that by signing this form, I do not waive any of my legal rights, nor does it relieve the study investigators their duty (liability), but merely indicates that I have been informed about the research study in which I am voluntarily agreeing to take part. A copy of this form will be availed to me.

Having understood all the information pertaining to this study I therefore agree to my participation in this study by appending my signature and name below.

Research Participant

Name:

Signature:

Date:

Tel number:

Makerere University College of Health Sciences; Supporting Informed
Healthcare Choices in Low-Income Countries Project.

RESEARCH PARTICIPANT INFORMED CONSENT FORM-ENGLISH

Project title: Supporting Informed Healthcare Choices in Low-Income Countries (SIHCLIC). Version 1.0 dated: 14 August 2012.

Sponsor: The Research Council of Norway

Study Principal Investigator: Prof. Nelson K. Sewankambo

Co-investigators: Ms. Allen Nsangi
Dr. Daniel Semakula

Addresses: Makerere University, College of Health Sciences
New Mulago Hospital Complex, Clinical Research Building, 2nd Floor
P.O Box 7072, Kampala, Uganda
Phone: 0312109456

Date/Revision: Version 1.1 (1st August 2014)

1. INTRODUCTION.

The Supporting Informed Healthcare Choices in Low-Income Countries (SIHCLIC) Project is a research collaboration that seeks to improve health literacy by developing and testing of resources that can be used by the public to appraise health information.

In Uganda, the study is being conducted by researchers from Makerere University College of Health Sciences and will involve continuous interaction with journalists, teachers and children.

The information in this document is meant to help you decide whether or not to take part in this study but first there a few things to note.

- You are being asked to participate in this research because you are a journalist/media practitioner or teacher or a potential recipient of information from journalists/media practitioners or teachers; and an adult of legal consenting age.
- We anticipate that once you agree to participate you will be in the study for a period of 5 years or less.
- You will be offered a copy of this form for your future reference.
- Please feel free to ask if you have any questions or concerns at any time before the start or during the conduct of the research.

2. WHY IS THIS RESEARCH BEING CONDUCTED?

The aim of this collaborative research project is to improve population health outcomes by improving health literacy in low-income countries. We will do this by developing and evaluating two strategies for improving health literacy: development and evaluation of mass media resources for the general public and the development and evaluation of teaching resources for school children.

SIHCLIC- English Informed Consent Form for journalists, teachers and their audiences Version 1.1 Aug 2014

Makerere University College of Health Sciences; Supporting Informed Healthcare Choices in Low-Income Countries Project.

3. HOW WILL THE STUDY BE CONDUCTED?

This project will be implemented using two strategies for improving health literacy:

- i) The development of mass media resources to improve the ability of the general public to understand and appraise information about the effects of health care.
- ii) The development of teaching resources for school children to improve their ability to appraise and use information about the effects of health care services/interventions made available to them.

These strategies will be evaluated in two community trials testing the effectiveness of the developed resources in improving health literacy among the target audiences for teachers and mass media practitioners/journalists.

The Research project will be conducted under 3 different phases, one following the other.

- Phase one will include: **Priority setting and stakeholder involvement.**
- The second phase will focus on **Resource development and user testing.**
- Phase three will concentrate on **Evaluation of the resources** developed.

4. POSSIBLE RISKS TO YOU:

We anticipate that your participation in the study/research presents no risk to you as an individual. However, participation in this study might in some way interfere with your work if you are required to participate in study activities during work hours.

5. POSSIBLE BENEFITS TO YOU.

There will be no direct benefit to you from participating in this study and there is no promise of gaining any material or financial benefit from the project currently or in the future.

Your participation in the study could contribute to gaining new knowledge that will be used to design resources aimed at improving population health outcomes by improving health literacy in low-income countries. You will be equipped with skills to enable you obtain, process and understand health information that you need to make appropriate healthcare decisions.

You will benefit from free health information.

6. COST TO THE PARTICIPANT.

You will incur no cost whatsoever other than time as a result of taking part in the study.

7. COMPENSATION.

You will not gain any form of compensation, monetary or otherwise for participating in the study but appropriate daily expenses in form of lunch and transport will be reimbursed if you attend any study-related meetings or workshops.

8. CONFIDENTIALITY.

The information you give during the conduct of this research will be kept confidential in accordance to the ethical standards agreed upon by the local and international organizations governing the conduct of research involving human participants.

Any information resulting from this study, if published in scientific journals or presented at scientific meetings, will not reveal your identity.

Makerere University College of Health Sciences; Supporting Informed Healthcare Choices in Low-Income Countries Project.

9. RIGHT TO REFUSE/WITHDRAW.

Your participation in this research is purely voluntary and you are free to decline to take part or withdraw at anytime without any repercussions.

10. QUESTIONS ABOUT THE RESEARCH

In case of any further questions, please contact Professor Nelson K. Sewankambo, the Principal Investigator at Makerere University College of Health Sciences, P.O. Box 7072, Kampala Uganda: Tel: 0414 530021 or Ms Allen Nsangi and Dr. Daniel Semakula, co-investigators on 0773333629 or 0716543000.

In case of questions in regards to research ethics, you may contact Prof. James Tumwine, Chairperson, MakCHS School of Medicine Research and Ethics Committee. Tel: 0414 531875.

11. DECLARATION OF CONSENT

The information about this study has been availed and explained to me and all my questions have been answered. I have read this form and I feel that I have had enough information and time to consider my decision to join the study. I fully understand that by signing this form, I do not waive any of my legal rights, nor does it relieve the study investigators their duty (liability), but merely indicates that I have been informed about the research study in which I am voluntarily agreeing to take part. A copy of this form will be availed to me.

Having understood all the information pertaining to this study I therefore agree to my participation in this study by appending my signature and name below.

Research Participant

Name:

Signature:

Date:

Tel number:
